

LEADERSHIP SKILLS OF PRINCIPALS AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated the role of leadership skills of principals in teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Three research questions and hypotheses were used to guide the study in line with the specific objectives. The study adopted a descriptive research design of the survey type and the population comprised principals from all 247 public senior secondary schools in the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. A sample size of 74 principals (30 males and 44 females), representing 30% of the entire population, was drawn using a simple random sampling technique. Data collection was conducted using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Principals' Leadership Skills and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (PLSTJQP). The instrument was validated by three experts, and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained using Cronbach's alpha through the test-retest method. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, while the null hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05 using the z-test. Findings revealed that leadership skills are the operational tools in influencing people, including secondary schools, to strive willingly and enthusiastically toward the achievement of organizational goals. Secondary school principals also encounter a myriad of challenges while performing their leadership roles. The study recommended that principals should possess proper leadership skills and techniques to enhance teachers' instructional delivery by encouraging staff welfare schemes, recommending staff for promotion exercises, making open commendations for teachers, and showing love/care for teachers to boost their morale. Principals should pay greater attention to

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their role performance, as it exerts a direct and significant influence on the performance of teachers.

Introduction

The effective management of human, material, and financial resources in any organization falls under the purview of administrative heads, who aim to achieve organizational goals. Organizations require efficient leadership to plan, organize, coordinate, control, budget, and account for collective efforts. Society has long emphasized education as a transformative tool for national development, placing onerous responsibilities on educational managers to advance teaching and learning through performance-based management. The principal serves as the fulcrum of this management team in secondary schools.

Scholars regard secondary education as Nigeria's pivotal level, bridging primary and tertiary education while preparing students for higher learning, self-reliance, and societal contributions. This objective hinges on the managerial prowess of the principal as an instructional leader, motivator, coordinator, adviser, planner, and supervisor. Babayemi (2006) asserted that principals must modify staff attitudes and motivate them to achieve educational goals. The managerial ability and leadership acumen of principals largely determine school success or failure, providing teachers with techniques to foster effective teaching and learning that reshape student behavior. Leadership skills, as organizational executives provide support services, create enabling environments for staff performance. Ololube (2013) emphasized that secondary school managerial techniques involve principals establishing conditions to enhance teachers' morale, commitment, and professional development.

As custodians and bookkeepers, principals perform routine administrative tasks to meet school objectives (Mbipom, 2006). Positioned at the hierarchy's apex, their activities directly or indirectly influence teachers, students, and non-teaching staff. Principals' role performance significantly shapes teachers' effectiveness, extending interactions to school boards, education commissions, and host communities, each with distinct expectations. Job performance, which is critical to organizational success, involves efficiently executing tasks with appropriate behaviors to meet goals. Peretomode, cited in Adeyemi (2010), links it to the participation of workers in daily operations. Principals must encourage teachers to achieve optimal results through apt leadership, need satisfaction, and motivation.

Principals not only set goals but also influence teachers' willingness to pursue them, distinguishing true leadership. Their roles—planning, coordination, supervision, decision-making, and motivation—coordinate resources for success. Effective leadership is essential; its failure undermines all else. Teachers' effectiveness drives school improvement and student academic performance, which is achieved through the skillful goal implementation of principals.

Statement of the problem

The secondary educational system is intended to prepare learners for future training and enable them to become useful and self-reliant in society. The fulfillment of these grand objectives relies on the successful administration of the system headed by the principal, who is saddled with the responsibility to coordinate the teaching and learning process. The principal coordinates the human, material, and physical assets in the educational system through different administrative methods, instructional supervision, motivation, and other factors to accomplish the ideal instructional goals. Regardless of the principals' and teachers' familiarity with the objectives of secondary education, it is profoundly astonishing to watch the frequencies of unsuitable conduct, examination malpractices, non-attendance lateness to school, teachers doing private business at official school hours, and dallying of teachers and students in Rivers State's public secondary schools. The aforementioned contravenes the objectives of secondary education. Despite all the efforts made by the government and other relevant stakeholders

to improve the quality of teachers' performance, these issues still prevail. This may have contributed to the poor academic performance of secondary school students recorded in internal and external examinations. Since all efforts may have yielded no significant results, the researcher wonders whether the leadership skills of principals compliment the job performance of secondary school teachers. Therefore, the thrust of this study is to investigate the link between principals' leadership skills and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study investigates the leadership skills of principals in relation to the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identifying various leadership skills required by principals for effective job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State
2. Ascertain the extent to which the effective leadership skills of principals could enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States.
3. Identify the leadership challenges faced by principals in the discharge of their leadership roles in Rivers State public senior secondary schools

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What leadership skills are required by male and female principals for effective job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent do male and female principals use leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States?
3. What are the leadership challenges facing male and female principals in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

Based on the abovementioned research questions, the following null hypotheses were tested at a significance level of 0.05:

1. No significant difference was found between the mean responses of male and female principals on various leadership skills required for effective job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. No significant difference was found between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which they utilized leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States.
3. No significant difference was found between the mean responses of male and female principals on the leadership challenges they face in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Review of the Related Literature

Theoretical Framework

Path-Goal Leadership Theory

This study adopted the Path-Goal theory of leadership developed by Evans (1970) and redefined by House (1971), as cited by Northouse (2013). Different scholars, including Evans (1970) and House (1971), stated that the Path-Goal theory of leadership is an outcome of Victor Vroom's Expectancy theory, which emphasizes that staff/employees' actions are carried out based on the expected reward to such action, and the level of reward

determines the rate of staff performance in the organization. However, Northouse (2013) recently stated that the Path-Goal theory of leadership is a “process in which leaders select specific behaviors that are best suited to the employees’ needs and the working environment so that they may best guide the employees through their path in the obtainment of their daily work activities (goal).” This implies that the leader has different leadership skills, styles, or behaviors and considers the most appropriate style in his/her leadership to suit the employees/staff needs and the working environment to attract the best action of the staff in the organization. The leader must motivate the employees/staff and satisfy their needs to enhance their job performance. House and Mitchell (1974) corroborated the views of the abovementioned scholars and added that the Path-Goal theory best explains the specific leadership skills applied by the leader to suit the “employees” and the “work environment” to enhance staff performance and achieve the organizational goal. The leader achieves his/her goal by identifying and motivating the staff, empowering them, and satisfying them. House (1971) further identified four leadership behavior variables: directive, supportive, participative, and achievement-oriented. Directive leadership implies that the leadership communicates organizational goals and expectations to the staff with the view of keeping the staff in the know. Supportive leadership entails the ability of the leader to be friendly in his/her relationship with subordinates. The leader identifies the needs of the staff and works out the best way to satisfy their needs, using staff satisfaction as a medium to improve staff performance. Participative leadership means that leaders give staff the opportunity to consult on organizational issues by allowing the staff to contribute to organizational decisions. Achievement-oriented leadership involves the leader’s ability to set challenging organizational goals for the organization’s staff and ask them to improve their performance to enhance organizational productivity.

The relevance of the Path-Goal theory to this study is based on the activities of the secondary school principal as a leader in the school and the leadership skills that the principal put on in the management of the school staff to achieve the school goal. The Path-Goal theory hinges on two variables: the “environment” representing the school environment and the “staff/subordinates” representing the school staff. The leadership skills of the principals of secondary schools in Rivers State affect their job performance. The theory proves that when the principal applies participatory leadership skills and style and motivates the staff, the latter are encouraged, and this enhances their job performance and goal achievement.

Conceptual Clarifications

(Source: Researcher, 2020)

Leadership as a concept has been given several meanings and interpretations by different scholars based on their schools of thought. Some see leadership as a field of study in social and management sciences; others see it as a

practical and professional skill to control others in administrative activities. At any point, leadership is given meaning to ensure its directional focus. According to Kruse (2013), “Leadership is a process of social influence, which maximizes the efforts of others toward the achievement of a goal.” In his view, Nworgu (1991) stated that leadership is the process of a leader influencing the activities of a group of people in an effort toward goal achievement. Similarly, Igbal, Anwar, and Haider (2015) see leadership as a process by which leaders can direct, guide, and influence others’ behavior and work toward the achievement of a specific goal in a given situation. In considering the above explanations, scholars see the executive as the leader in a given situation, and the leader is the human factor that can influence other resources (human and material) to achieve the set goal. Scholars further see leadership from different perspectives, firstly, as a “process,” which implies that leadership requires a series of actions to achieve the desired result.

Second, as a “social influence,” leadership requires that one is set to influence others’ activities toward a particular purpose. Third, as “goal achieving,” the cardinal objective of leadership is to achieve the set goal in a given situation. Considering the above views, this study tends to observe a gap in the literature, particularly the inability of scholars to state the objective or goal that the leadership is set to achieve. Yes, leadership is set to achieve a goal, but whose goal? Is it the goal of the leader, the subordinate, or the organization? In another development, Koudri (1999) opined that leadership involves dealing and coping with changes, focusing on the long-term and the big picture, not always doing so to save himself, but in fact, taking risks and concentrating on people and their values, not just the bottom line. According to Collins (1995), the most powerfully transformed executives possess a paradoxical mixture of personal humility and professional will, and they are both timid and ferocious. They focus on empowerment rather than control for employee performance development. In the views of Collins (1995) and Koudri (1999), leadership is personalized as a risk bearer who is even helpless in the face of organizational risk but is determined to impact value on others with the view of developing them and utilizing them to achieve set goals.

Consequently, leadership involves an individual’s capacity and knowledge in an executive position to influence others. Considering the views of different scholars on leadership, Trevisani (2016) identified leadership as a holistic approach in controlling others and achieving set goals. He further explained leadership in six perspectives:

- Higher levels of physical power, need to display power and control others, superiority, ability to generate fear, or need for a powerful group protector (Primal Leadership);
- Superior mental energies, superior motivational forces, perceivable in communication and behaviors, lack of fear, courage, determination (PEL);
- Higher abilities in managing the overall picture (Macro-Leadership);
- Higher abilities in specialized tasks (Micro-Leadership);
- Higher ability to manage task execution (project leadership);
- And higher levels of values, wisdom, and spirituality (Spiritual Leadership), where any leader derives its leadership from a unique mix of one or more of the former factors (p. 21). The above views prompted Soni (2012) to describe principals as leaders in secondary schools, with the responsibility of controlling other staff to achieve school objectives. This study corroborated the views of Soni (2012) and Trevisani (2016, p. 21) on leadership issues and defined leadership as the ability to control others to achieve the set goals in a given organization. It could be the goal of an organization or an individual but is guided by the set goals.

Leadership Skills

One of the numerous approaches to leadership is an approach based on the skills or knowledge that leaders should possess. Over the years, researchers have addressed the question of what skills leaders should possess (Bass, 1990). The approach to leadership from the standpoint of skills started with the article by Robert Katz, entitled "Skills of an Effective Administrator", which was published in 1955 in Harvard Business Review. The standpoint of skills was meant to overcome the standpoint of properties, according to which the concept of leadership capacities depends on the inherited personality traits. (Northouse, 2010). The standpoint of skills makes it possible to teach leadership. In Markovic and Ljajic (2016), Katz claimed that leaders can acquire and develop skills, while we are born with personality traits (Katz, 1955). Katz proposed three groups of skills: technical, interpersonal, and abstract thinking skills. Technical skills are related to knowledge and expertise in a particular line of business. Interpersonal skills refer to the skills and ability to work with people, and abstract thinking skills relate to the ability to work with ideas. Depending on the management level, some skills are needed more than others. In the first line of management, technical skills are more necessary. Line managers, executive managers, and supervisors are on the first line who need to mention and demonstrate to employees how to perform a particular job. Managers in the middle line of leadership mostly need interpersonal skills. Managers in the middle line act as buffers or buffer zones between the highest levels of management and direct supervisors. They transmit instructions and information from the bottom down to the top level, and vice versa. Top-line managers require conceptual skills, that is, abstract thinking skills that enable understanding of the interrelationship between different parts and the dynamics of impact, which is essential for good decision-making. Numerous studies started in 1990, pointing to the importance of the skills of leaders in solving complex organizational problems. Mumford, Zaccaro, Harding, Jacobs, and Fleishman (2000) conceived the skills model comprising five elements:

1. Abilities,
2. Individual properties,
3. Leaders' performance
4. Work experience and
5. Environmental impacts.

The backbone of the abovementioned model consists of the following abilities: problem solving skills, social judgment skills, and knowledge. The problem-solving skill includes the ability to define and understand the problem, collect data on the problem, and form a creative approach to it and integrate solutions and their application in an appropriate time frame (Mumford, Zaccaro, Connelly, & Marks, 2000). A skill "social judgment" implies understanding of people and social situations, such as understanding, sensitivity to your ideas, and the behavior of people receiving them. Mumford et al. allocate the following skills: assuming perspective, social perceptual sensitivity, behavior flexibility, and social performance. Assuming the perspective refers to the understanding of other people's opinions about a particular problem. Social perceptual sensitivity implies an understanding of how other people work, what is important to them, and their motives. Behavioral flexibility means the ability to change behavior and adapt it in line with others' views and needs. Social performance comprises several skills, including the ability to convey the vision to employees, the ability to persuade, and the ability to settle conflicts. Individual characteristics include general cognitive abilities, crystallized intelligence, motivation, and personality. General cognitive abilities include perceptual competence, i.e., detecting data speed, data processing, divergent and creative thinking ability, and conclusion drawing ability. General cognitive abilities are inherited and form the basis for problem-solving skills development. These skills are often called fluid intelligence. Crystallized intelligence develops over time and through experience. People can learn how to

make conclusions, organize information, and communicate with others. They also learn the techniques and approaches to problem solving. Motivation is a key factor in leadership.

However, to realize leadership, a person must want to lead; then to be able to impact others, to do it in a responsible manner, and to be committed to the organization's social welfare. Individual characteristics comprise the personality of leaders with the following characteristics: tolerance, openness, flexibility, and all other features that contribute to successful leadership. All previously described elements should lead to the successful execution of leadership, which includes the successful resolution of problems and high performance.

Managerial Skills

It is noteworthy that managerial skills are essential capabilities that determine the extent to which an executive or head of an organization (school) will succeed. Okoye (2007) viewed managerial skills as the ability to plan, control, organize, and direct an educational enterprise's operations to achieve the objective target set for the educational system as a whole. Fullan (2005) defined managerial skills as competencies required for effective and efficient planning, staffing, organizing, coordinating, controlling, and decision-making. Therefore, managerial skills are the ability, knowledge, and experience needed to accomplish management tasks and achieve organizational goals and objectives. Principal managerial skills refer to the ability to skillfully and successfully plan, supervise, organize, coordinate, control, make decisions, and initiate actions that would aid and encourage teachers to actualize the school's goals and objectives. Notwithstanding, managers are at liberty to develop managerial skills that would help in the actualization of organizational (school) goals and objectives. Scholars have specified some result-oriented skills used by successful managers in both private and public organizations. In Ifediato (2017), Katz elaborated on these globally accepted managerial skills as developed by Fayol, which are conceptual, human, and technical skills.

1. **Conceptual Skill:** This skill enables the manager to coordinate all activities of the different parts of the organization. The ability to visualize or see the organization as a whole. It includes analytical, creative, and initiative skills. According to Katz in Ifediato, top-level management primarily requires conceptual skills. This is because they spend more time planning, organizing, and problem-solving. It helps them to solve problems for the benefit of the entire organization and also helps the managers to fix goals for the entire organization and plan for every situation that may arise from time to time.

2. **Human Skill:** This skill includes the ability to work with and motivate and inspire people. It implies an interpersonal relationship. It helps managers understand, communicate, and work with others. It makes the manager a cohesive team leader who understands and listens to various group members. Because all managers must interact and work with people, this skill is essential.

3. **Technical Skill:** This skill is most needed at the top management level. In this skill, more time is spent planning, organizing, and problem solving. It has to do with proficiency in activities such as managerial processes, procedures, and strategies. Managers need this skill to design and put into operation policies and plans. Technical skills help managers use different machines and tools effectively.

Job performance of teachers

Performance is something a single person does. The performance of teachers in schools is highly affected by motivation. When motivated, teachers' performance automatically reached a high level. In school, the teacher's performance can be mapped well by arranging training programs for the teachers, and they will be motivated and their confidence will also increase. Motivation has a direct and positive effect on job performance when effort is properly accounted for. Effort has a positive effect on job performance. The idea that motivated employees are

more productive was held through the 1970s. However, obtaining support for the view that motivation has a significant effect on job performance was difficult.

Griffin (2005) explained that an individual's performance is determined by three factors: motivation, work environment, and ability to do work. Chandrasekar (2011) examined the positive and negative impacts of the workplace environment on employee morale, productivity, and job performance. If the workplace environment is not liked by the employees, they get demotivated and their performance is affected. Poorly designed work timings, unsuitable authorities or duties, lack of appreciation, and lack of opportunity for personal decision-making. People working in such an environment are not satisfied; they feel stress on themselves, which impacts their job performance. Adeyemi (2010) investigated the relationship between the leadership styles of principals and the job performance of teachers in secondary schools. He found that the principals mostly used the democratic leadership style in schools compared to the autocratic style. It was the most commonly used leadership style by principals in schools. His study also determined a direct relationship between the leadership styles used by principals and the job performance of teachers. His study concluded that the performance of teachers is better in schools where principals have an autocratic leadership style than in schools where principals have a democratic style of leadership. Thus, the autocratic style is the best style of leadership that can improve teachers' productivity and performance in schools. He also recommended that principals should use both autocratic and democratic leadership styles in their schools to improve the job performance of teachers. In certain situations, they could apply the autocratic style where it is applicable, while in some situations, they could use the democratic style. Organizational success can only be achieved by satisfied and motivated employees and good leadership (Malik, Danish, & Usman, 2010). Therefore, a good leadership style is required to lead teachers and enhance their efficiency in schools.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive research design. This approach was adopted because the researcher intends to identify the leadership skills of principals in relation to the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study population consisted of 247 public senior secondary schools in the 23 local government areas of Rivers State. The study sample consisted of 74 principals (male principals = 30 and female principals = 44), which represented 30 % of the entire population, using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled "Principals' Leadership Skills for Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire" (PLSTJPQ). The instrument was validated by two experts in the Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counseling and one in Educational Management departments, University of Port Harcourt. A reliability coefficient of 0.78 (78 percent reliability) was obtained using Cronbach's alpha through the test-retest method. The research questions were answered using the mean, standard deviation, and rank order, while the null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using the z-test. Tables were constructed with respect to the demands of the respective research questions and hypotheses, and a criterion mean of 2.50 was used.

Results

Data presentation and analysis to answer research questions and hypotheses

Research Question One: What leadership skills are required by male and female principals for effective job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of various leadership skills required by male and female principals for effective job performance of teachers in Rivers State public senior secondary schools

S/N	Items	Male Principals N = 30		Decision	Female Principals N = 44		Decision	Mean set	Overall Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁		\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
1	Skills for team building and collaboration	2.51	0.11	Agree	2.56	0.13	Agree	2.54	Agree
2	Ability to coordinate with diverse people	2.67	0.22	Agree	2.80	0.19	Agree	2.74	Agree
3	Strong written and verbal communication skills	2.89	0.07	Agree	2.77	0.12	Agree	2.83	Agree
4	Organize and encourage professional development seminars and in-service training	3.00	0.10	Agree	3.02	0.16	Agree	3.01	Agree
5	Remain up-to-date on current educational administration trends or concerns	2.90	0.09	Agree	2.78	0.11	Agree	2.84	Agree
6	Promote school spirit events	2.67	0.24	Agree	2.60	0.18	Agree	2.64	Agree
7	Encourage community involvement and participation in promotional events	2.51	0.33	Agree	2.54	0.24	Agree	2.53	Agree
8	Maintaining an optimistic, can-do attitude	2.56	0.22	Agree	2.51	0.19	Agree	2.54	Agree
9	Offer positive reinforcement to teachers and students	2.50	0.24	Agree	2.63	0.23	Agree	2.57	Agree
10	Play an active role in individualized education plans/programs	2.50	0.12	Agree	2.54	0.10	Agree	2.52	Agree
11	Drive learning and success for all students	2.87	0.08	Agree	2.89	0.07	Agree	2.88	Agree
12	Parent relationship building	2.80	0.33	Agree	2.71	0.25	Agree	2.76	Agree
13	Share best practices with both experienced and new staff	2.81	0.23	Agree	2.87	0.21	Agree	2.84	Agree
14	Understand school policies and expectations of the superintendent	3.10	0.11	Agree	3.08	0.14	Agree	3.09	Agree
15	Retain a professional leadership appearance	2.90	0.13	Agree	2.88	0.15	Agree	2.89	Agree
16	Managing people, data, and processes to improve schools	2.50	0.24	Agree	2.53	0.20	Agree	2.52	Agree
17	Creating an optimal learning environment	2.51	0.15	Agree	2.73	0.18	Agree	2.68	Agree

18	Cultivating Leadership in the School Community	2.63	0.23	Agree	2.87	0.17	Agree	2.75	Agree
19	Improving instruction	2.52	0.33	Agree	2.56	0.29	Agree	2.54	Agree
20	Setting high expectations	2.76	0.34	Agree	2.81	0.32	Agree	2.79	Agree
Aggregate Mean and SD values		2.71	0.20	Agree	2.87	0.18	Agree	2.79	Agree

Table 1 shows that the average mean score of male principals was 2.71 with a standard deviation of 0.20 and that of female principals was 2.87 with a standard deviation of 0.18. The aggregate mean score of male and female principals was 2.79. Judging by the results, Table 1 reveals that all the items had a mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, the respondents agreed on the various leadership skills required by principals for effective job performance of teachers in River State secondary schools.

Research Question Two: To what extent do male and female principals use leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States?

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of male and female principals on the use of leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States

S/N	Items	Male Principals N = 30		Decision	Female Principals N = 42		Decision	Mean set	Overall Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁		\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
21	The guidance of the principal in helping teachers plan relevant and acceptable goals and instructional objectives enhances the job performance of teachers	2.78	0.35	Agree	2.80	0.29	Agree	2.79	Agree
22	Principals exhibiting the skill of helping teachers in planning learning opportunities and experiences that will facilitate the achievement of the educational goals and objectives improves teachers' effectiveness.	2.89	0.28	Agree	2.58	0.31	Agree	2.74	Agree
23	The development of highly motivated staff by the principal by stimulating the teacher's interest in teaching would sustain the job performance of teachers.	2.67	0.13	Agree	2.53	0.17	Agree	2.60	Agree

24	Helping teachers develop skills and attitudes improves job performance	2.51	0.41	Agree	2.50	0.37	Agree	2.50	Agree
25	Coordinating the varieties of teaching units in the school by the principal improves the performance of teachers	2.90	0.14	Agree	2.78	0.18	Agree	2.84	Agree
26	Helping teachers professionally develop triggers their job involvement and performance	2.51	0.11	Agree	2.62	0.10	Agree	2.57	Agree
27	Regular communication and interaction with teachers improves teachers' work attitude and job performance	2.52	0.18	Agree	2.49	0.22	Disagree	2.51	Agree
Aggregate Mean and SD values		2.68	0.23	Agree	2.61	0.23	Agree	2.65	Agree

Table 2 shows that the average mean score of male principals was 2.68 with a standard deviation of 0.23, whereas that of female principals was 2.61 with a standard deviation of 0.23. The aggregate mean of both respondents was 2.65. Table 2 shows that all the items had a mean above the criterion mean of 2.5. Thus, the respondents agreed that to a large extent, male and female principals use leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States.

Research Question Three: What leadership challenges do male and female principals face in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the leadership challenges faced by male and female principals in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

S/N	Items	Male Principals N = 30		Decision	Female Principals N = 42		Decision	Mean set	Overall Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁		\bar{X}_2	SD ₂			
28	External influences on the principal	2.51	0.33	Agree	2.50	0.30	Agree	2.51	Agree
29	Non-compliance of teachers to principal's directives	2.67	0.26	Agree	2.64	0.23	Agree	2.66	Agree
30	Unguided Principals' Objectives and Leadership Focus	2.89	0.13	Agree	2.90	0.11	Agree	2.90	Agree
31	Inadequately skilled staff to implement the principal directive	3.00	0.11	Agree	3.03	0.17	Agree	3.02	Agree

32	Inability of the principals to supervise the job performance of staff in the schools	2.90	0.14	Agree	2.79	0.12	Agree	2.85	Agree
33	Lesser authority to discipline teachers who were not committed to their duties based on external interference from the secondary school board	2.67	0.44	Agree	2.54	0.37	Agree	2.61	Agree
34	Lack of availability of funds directly to the accounts of schools to run the schools	2.51	0.41	Agree	2.54	0.43	Agree	2.53	Agree
35	Incessant transfer of teachers	2.56	0.13	Agree	2.67	0.11	Agree	2.62	Agree
36	Teachers' attitude	2.50	0.28	Agree	2.53	0.25	Agree	2.52	Agree
37	Low commitment of teachers	2.50	0.35	Agree	2.54	0.33	Agree	2.52	Agree
Aggregate Mean and SD values		2.67	0.26	Agree	2.67	0.24	Agree	2.67	Agree

Table 3 shows that the aggregate mean score of male and female principals was 2.67, while male principals had an average mean score of 2.67 (SD = 0.26) and female principals had an average mean score of 2.67 (SD = 0.24). Judging by the results, Table 3 reveals that all the items had a mean above the criterion mean of 2.50. Respondents agreed on the leadership challenges facing male and female principals in the use of leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on various leadership skills required for effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of z-test on mean responses of male and female principals on various leadership skills required for effective job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Categories	N	X	SD	Df	P	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	30	2.71	0.20	72	0.05	3.54	1.96	Ho1 Rejected
Female	44	2.87	0.18					

Table 4 shows that the calculated z value of 3.54 is less than the critical z value of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 72. The null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on various leadership skills required for effective job performance in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which they use leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in Rivers State public senior secondary schools.

Table 5: Summary of the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which they use leadership skills to enhance the job performance of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers States.

Categories	N	X	SD	Df	P	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	30	2.68	0.23	72	0.05	1.25	1.96	Ho2 Rejected

Female	44	2.61	0.23
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Table 5 shows that the calculated z value of 1.25 is less than the critical z value of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 72. The null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the extent to which their effective leadership skills could enhance the job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Rivers States.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on the leadership challenges they face in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job of teachers in Rivers State's public senior secondary schools.

Table 6. Summary of z-test on mean responses of male and female principals on leadership challenges they face in utilizing leadership skills to enhance the job of teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Categories	N	X	SD	Df	P	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Male	30	2.67	0.26	72	0.05	0.00	1.96	Ho3
Female	44	2.67	0.24					Accepted

As shown in Table 6, the z calculated value of 0.00 is less than the z critical value of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance with a degree of freedom of 72. The hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female principals on principals' leadership challenges in discharge of their leadership roles in Rivers State secondary schools.

Discussion of the Findings

The study revealed that all the items centered on the various leadership skills required by principals to enhance teachers' performance were accepted by the respondents. The test for hypothesis one also showed that the calculated z value of 3.54 was greater than the critical z value of 1.96 at the chosen level of significance; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This finding validated the study of Adwella (2014), who saw leadership as an operational tool in influencing people to strive willingly and enthusiastically toward the achievement of organizational goals, including those of secondary schools. Nworgu (1991), Omolayo (2000), and Aghenta (2001) explained leadership as a process of a leader influencing the activities of a group of people in an effort to attain the organizational goal. As in the case of a secondary school, a leader requires diverse leadership skills in dealing with staff, taking into cognizance that human beings have different emotions, attitudes, and expectations.

Finding on the extent to which principals use effective leadership skills to enhance teachers' job performance revealed that effective leadership skills improved teachers' performance to a great extent. Therefore, school administrators should be well aware of the impact of leadership on staff performance.

Additionally, findings on the challenges faced by principals in the use of leadership skills revealed that inadequately skilled staff to implement the principal's directives is an impediment to the achievement of set goals. In the test of hypothesis three, the respondents were in unison, proving that principals faced leadership challenges; hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This finding is in line with Wilson (2016), who observed that the aforementioned leadership challenges affect principal leadership in schools and lead to staff inefficiency and underperformance.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this study is that principal leadership skills are paramount to the enhancement of teachers' job performance in Rivers State secondary schools. The study itemized the various leadership skills that secondary

school principals should adopt to ensure teachers' performance, as it plays an important role in an education system. If teachers are ill-treated and under-performing, then they cannot give their best, which invariably affects the realization of their educational goals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

1. Only suitably qualified and competent professionals with the right leadership skills should be appointed as head of secondary schools.
2. Principals should possess proper leadership skills and techniques to enhance teachers' instructional delivery by encouraging staff welfare schemes, recommending staff for promotion exercises, making open commendations for teachers, and showing love/care for teachers to boost their morale. Principals should pay more attention to their role performance as it has a direct/significant influence on the performance of teachers.
3. Principals should develop the leadership of delegating functions to teachers according to their area of expertise, as this would result in increased participation in the actualization of school goals and objectives.
4. Principals should provide a platform for vertical and horizontal communication flow. Proper communication strategies/channels should be adopted to allow teachers' participation and activeness in school policies, projects, and programs. Information necessary for teachers to discharge their duties on time should also be communicated to them.

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